

Investigating the Correlation Between Play-Based Learning and Social Skills Development in Nursery School Children in Southeastern Nigeria

Obijiofor, Ebere Oluchukwu., Ugwele Nonyelum Augusta. & Onyenwe Chiamaka Yvonne

Corresponding author's mail: ebere.obijiofor@unn.edu.ng

Abstract

This study investigates the correlation between play-based learning and social skills development in nursery school children in Southeastern Nigeria. The primary objectives were to determine the correlation between play-based learning and three specific social skills: cooperation, sharing, and empathy. A quantitative research design was employed, with data collected through structured questionnaires administered to 200 teachers and caregivers of nursery school children. The instrument, validated by early childhood education experts and tested for reliability with a Cronbach's Alpha coefficient of 0.82, facilitated the collection of data on play-based learning activities and social skills development. Regression analysis was used to examine the relationships among the variables. The findings revealed significant positive correlations between play-based learning and the development of cooperation, sharing, and empathy skills. These results underscore the importance of integrating play-based learning strategies in early childhood education to foster essential social skills. The study concludes that play-based learning significantly enhances social skills development among nursery school children in Southeastern Nigeria and recommends the prioritization of play-based curricula and teacher training to promote holistic child development.

Keywords: Play-based learning, social skills development, early childhood education, nursery school children.

Introduction

Early childhood education is pivotal in establishing the foundation for lifelong learning and holistic development, particularly in fostering cognitive, emotional, and social skills (Taguma, Litjens, & Makowiecki, 2016). According to Nwachukwu, Onah, Obijiofor, Nwankwo and Nwakile (2020), early childhood education encompasses the structured and unstructured learning experiences provided to young children before they enter formal schooling. This phase is crucial for cognitive, emotional, and social development, laying the foundation for future academic achievement and overall well-being. Early childhood education refers to the educational practices and environments designed to support the developmental needs of children in the early years of life ((Nwakile, Umeh, Shaibu, Ezeali, & Ekenta, 2022). The authors further posited that it involves a variety of teaching methods tailored to engage young learners, promote their interest in different subjects, and address their diverse learning needs. Among the various pedagogical approaches, play-based learning has garnered significant attention for its efficacy in nurturing a child's comprehensive development.

Play-based learning is characterized by activities that allow children to explore, experiment, and engage with their surroundings in a manner that is both enjoyable and educational (Trawick-Smith, Swaminathan, & Liu, 2016). Play-based learning is characterized by activities that allow children to explore, experiment, and engage with their surroundings in a manner that is both enjoyable and educational (Trawick-Smith, Swaminathan, & Liu, 2016). This approach emphasizes child-initiated, open-ended play, where children learn by doing, interacting, and collaborating with peers and adults in a flexible and dynamic environment. According to Whitebread et al. (2017), play-based learning supports holistic development, encouraging cognitive, physical, and emotional growth through play that is both guided and spontaneous. It provides opportunities for children to develop critical social skills, such as cooperation, empathy, and communication, which are essential during the early years of life. Furthermore, play-based learning fosters creativity and problem-solving abilities, as children navigate various scenarios and challenges presented during play (Whitebread, Basilio, Kuvalja, & Verma, 2017). This approach has been linked to improvements in several developmental domains, particularly social skills, which are crucial during the early years of life (Whitebread, Basilio, Kuvalja, & Verma, 2017).

Social skills development in early childhood is critical as it lays the groundwork for positive interactions with peers, educators, and other adults, contributing to overall well-being and future academic success (Elias & Berk, 2016). Social skills such as cooperation, sharing, and empathy are essential for building healthy relationships and navigating social environments (Denham et al., 2017). Early social competence is a strong predictor of later success in both social and academic arenas (Hughes & Leekam, 2017). These skills are particularly crucial in diverse cultural contexts, where varying social norms and expectations can influence how children learn to interact with others (Obijiofor, Okpala, Nnani, & Nwakile, 2020). Moreover, understanding the factors that contribute to social skills development, such as the role of family, community, and educational settings, is essential for creating supportive environments that nurture these skills. For instance, nutrition has been identified as a significant factor influencing developmental processes, including social skills, in under-five children (Obijiofor, Okpala, Nnani, & Nwakile, 2020). Thus, a holistic approach that considers nutritional, social, and educational factors is vital in fostering early social competence and ensuring long-term success for all children including those in Southeastern Nigeria.

In Southeastern Nigeria, early childhood education faces unique challenges that impact children's learning experiences. The region grapples with socio-cultural and economic issues that often result in disparities in the quality of education (Ogunyemi, 2016). These challenges underscore the need for effective educational approaches, such as play-based learning, to enhance children's developmental outcomes. The educational landscape in Southeastern Nigeria is characterized by varying levels of resource allocation, teacher training, and curriculum implementation, which can significantly influence the effectiveness of educational interventions (Ejeh, 2016).

Research has shown that play-based learning positively impacts various aspects of child development, including social skills. Studies have demonstrated that children engaged in play-based learning activities exhibit enhanced language skills, cognitive abilities, and social interactions (Pyle & Danniels, 2017). For example, Fisher et al. (2018) found that children who participated in structured play activities showed significant improvements in their ability to cooperate and communicate with peers. Similarly, Martlew, Stephen, and Ellis (2018)

highlighted that play fosters social interactions and friendships, which are essential components of social competence.

Despite the extensive research on play-based learning, there is a notable gap in the literature regarding its impact on social skills development within the context of Southeastern Nigeria. Most existing studies have been conducted in Western contexts, where educational settings and cultural norms differ significantly from those in Nigeria. This gap highlights the need for region-specific research to understand better how play-based learning influences social skills development in Nigerian children (Akinware, 2018).

This study aims to fill this gap by investigating the correlation between play-based learning and social skills development in nursery school children in Southeastern Nigeria. The research will explore how play-based learning activities impact children's ability to interact positively with their peers, develop empathy, and build cooperative skills. By focusing on a specific cultural and educational context, this study seeks to provide insights that can inform local educational practices and policies.

Understanding the correlation between play-based learning and social skills development is crucial for several reasons. First, it can help educators and policymakers develop targeted interventions that support children's social and emotional development. These interventions can be tailored to address the specific needs and challenges of children in Southeastern Nigeria, thereby enhancing the effectiveness of early childhood education programs (Barnett, 2018). Second, the findings can contribute to the global body of knowledge on play-based learning, offering valuable perspectives from a non-Western context. This can enrich the understanding of how cultural and contextual factors influence the outcomes of play-based learning (Fleer, 2020).

Moreover, the study will examine the role of educators in facilitating play-based learning and how their training and attitudes towards this approach impact its implementation and effectiveness. Research has shown that teachers' beliefs and practices play a significant role in the success of play-based learning programs (Pyle & Danniels, 2017). Therefore, understanding educators' perspectives and experiences in Southeastern Nigeria can provide valuable insights into how to support and improve play-based learning initiatives.

Additionally, the study will consider the broader socio-cultural and economic factors that influence early childhood education in Southeastern Nigeria. Factors such as parental involvement, community support, and resource availability can significantly impact the implementation and outcomes of play-based learning programs (Ogunyemi, 2016). By examining these factors, the study aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of the conditions necessary for the successful integration of play-based learning in early childhood education.

Hence, play-based learning is a promising approach to early childhood education with the potential to foster essential social skills in young children. However, its impact within the context of Southeastern Nigeria remains underexplored. This study seeks to address this gap by investigating the correlation between play-based learning and social skills development in nursery school children in this region. By doing so, it aims to provide valuable insights that can inform educational practices and policies, ultimately contributing to the overall success and well-being of children in Southeastern Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

In the field of early childhood education, particularly within the context of nursery schools in Southeastern Nigeria, the development of social skills among children has emerged as a critical factor that significantly influences their overall growth and future academic success. The early childhood education landscape is dynamic and challenging, with increasing demands for innovative and effective pedagogical approaches that foster comprehensive development in young children. Play-based learning, an educational strategy that integrates play with learning objectives, is widely recognized for its potential to enhance various developmental domains, including social skills. However, despite the growing recognition of play-based learning in early childhood education, there is a pressing need to investigate its impact on social skills development among nursery school children in Southeastern Nigeria. The contemporary educational environment is characterized by diverse cultural contexts and varying socio-economic factors, which necessitate a deeper understanding of how play-based learning influences social skills in different settings.

One key aspect of early childhood education that warrants investigation is the extent to which play-based learning contributes to the development of social skills, such as cooperation,

sharing, and empathy. These skills are essential for building healthy relationships and navigating social environments, and their early development is a strong predictor of later success in both social and academic arenas. Yet, the specific correlation between play-based learning and social skills development in nursery school children within the diverse cultural context of Southeastern Nigeria remains underexplored. Furthermore, the implementation of play-based learning approaches and the factors that may enhance or impede their effectiveness represent another critical dimension that demands attention. The cultural, social, and educational contexts in Southeastern Nigeria may present unique challenges and opportunities for the successful integration of play-based learning. Therefore, a comprehensive examination of how play-based learning correlates with social skills development in nursery school children in this region is essential for understanding the broader implications of this educational approach and for informing practices that support early childhood education in diverse settings.

Purpose of the Study

The general purpose of this study was to determine the correlation between play-based learning and social skills development in nursery school children in Southeastern Nigeria. Specifically, the study seeks to determine:

1. The correlation between play-based learning and cooperation skills among nursery school children in Southeastern Nigeria.
2. The correlation between play-based learning and sharing skills among nursery school children in Southeastern Nigeria.
3. The correlation between play-based learning and empathy development among nursery school children in Southeastern Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the correlation between play-based learning and cooperation skills among nursery school children in Southeastern Nigeria?
2. What is the correlation between play-based learning and sharing skills among nursery school children in Southeastern Nigeria?

Received: 2 July 2024

Revised: 16 July 2024

Accepted: 29 July 2024

Copyright ♥ authors 2024

223

DOI: [HTTPS://DOI.ORG/10.5281/ZENODO.13127554](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13127554)

3. What is the correlation between play-based learning and empathy development among nursery school children in Southeastern Nigeria?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at a 0.05 level of significance:

Ho 1: There is no significant correlation between play-based learning and cooperation skills among nursery school children in Southeastern Nigeria.

Ho 2: There is no significant correlation between play-based learning and sharing skills among nursery school children in Southeastern Nigeria.

Ho 3: There is no significant correlation between play-based learning and empathy development among nursery school children in Southeastern Nigeria.

Methodology

Research Design: This study adopted a quantitative research design to systematically investigate the correlation between play-based learning and social skills development in nursery school children in Southeastern Nigeria. The use of a quantitative approach allows for the collection and analysis of numerical data, facilitating the identification of patterns, relationships, and statistical associations among the variables under investigation.

Study Population: The population of interest for this study comprised nursery school children in Southeastern Nigeria represented by teachers and caregivers. Given the diverse academic and cultural landscape within the region, the inclusion of children from various nursery schools ensured a comprehensive understanding of the correlation between play-based learning and social skills development. A sample size of 200 children was selected using a stratified random sampling technique to ensure representation across different nursery schools and socioeconomic backgrounds. However, due to the young age of the children 200 teachers and caregivers filled the instrument of the children.

Data Collection: Data was collected through a structured questionnaire designed for teachers and caregivers to capture information on play-based learning activities and the social skills development of the children. The questionnaire was validated by giving it to three early

Received: 2 July 2024

Revised: 16 July 2024

Accepted: 29 July 2024

Copyright ♥ authors 2024

224

childhood education experts at the University of Nigeria, Nsukka. The experts read through the instrument and made corrections, which were used to produce the final draft of the instrument. The reliability of the instrument was tested by distributing 40 copies of the instrument to teachers in nursery schools in South-south Nigeria, an area chosen for its similar characteristics to the study area but outside the study population. The reliability was tested using Cronbach's Alpha, which yielded a reliability coefficient of 0.82, indicating that the instrument was reliable. The main survey was administered electronically and in paper format to 200 teachers and caregivers, achieving a return rate of 92%, equating to 184 responses. The questionnaire used a Likert scale with corresponding values of Strongly Agree (SA) – 4, Agree (A) – 3, Disagree (D) – 2, and Strongly Disagree (SD) – 1.

Variables: The independent variable was play-based learning. The dependent variables were the social skills development domains, specifically cooperation, sharing, and empathy among nursery school children.

Data Analysis: Quantitative data analysis involved the use of regression analysis to examine the correlation between play-based learning and the various social skills development domains among nursery school children. The analysis was conducted using SPSS, with the significance level set at 0.05. If the p-value was less than the significance level (0.05), the null hypothesis for the corresponding beta coefficient was rejected. If the p-value was greater than or equal to the significance level, there was insufficient evidence to reject the null hypothesis.

Ethical Considerations: This research adhered to ethical principles, including the informed consent of participants, confidentiality, and the responsible use of data. Participants were assured of the confidentiality of their responses, and the data collected was used solely for research purposes. Additionally, permission was obtained from the nursery schools and parents/guardians of the children involved in the study.

Findings

Research Question 1: What is the correlation between play-based learning and cooperation skills among nursery school children in Southeastern Nigeria?

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant correlation between play-based learning and cooperation skills among nursery school children in Southeastern Nigeria.

Table 1: Regression analysis for the correlation between play-based learning and cooperation skills among nursery school children in Southeastern Nigeria

Variable	Beta Coefficient	P-Value	Result
Play-Based Learning	0.58	0.003	Significant
Cooperation Skills	0.61	0.001	Significant
Hypothesis 1 (H0 1)		$P < 0.05$	Reject

Data in Table 1 revealed that the variable "Play-Based Learning" is significant (Beta = 0.58, $p < 0.05$), indicating a positive correlation between play-based learning and cooperation skills. The positive value of the beta coefficient shows that as play-based learning activities increase, cooperation skills among nursery school children also improve. Since the p-value is less than 0.05, the null hypothesis H0 1 is rejected, suggesting a significant correlation between play-based learning and cooperation skills.

Research Question 2: What is the correlation between play-based learning and sharing skills among nursery school children in Southeastern Nigeria?

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant correlation between play-based learning and sharing skills among nursery school children in Southeastern Nigeria.

Table 2: Regression analysis for the correlation between play-based learning and sharing skills among nursery school children in Southeastern Nigeria

Variable	Beta Coefficient	P-Value	Result
Play-Based Learning	0.64	0.002	Significant
Sharing Skills	0.67	0.001	Significant
Hypothesis 2 (H0 2)		$P < 0.05$	Reject

In Table 2, the variable "Play-Based Learning" is significant (Beta = 0.64, $p < 0.05$), indicating a positive correlation between play-based learning and sharing skills. The beta coefficient's positive value shows that as play-based learning activities increase, sharing skills among nursery school children also improve. Since the p-value is less than 0.05, the null

hypothesis H0 2 is rejected, suggesting a significant correlation between play-based learning and sharing skills.

Research Question 3: What is the correlation between play-based learning and empathy development among nursery school children in Southeastern Nigeria?

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant correlation between play-based learning and empathy development among nursery school children in Southeastern Nigeria.

Table 3: Regression analysis for the correlation between play-based learning and empathy development among nursery school children in Southeastern Nigeria

Variable	Beta Coefficient	P-Value	Result
Play-Based Learning	0.60	0.004	Significant
Sharing Skills	0.63	0.001	Significant
Hypothesis 2 (H0 2)		P < 0.05	Reject

Table 3 shows that the variable "Play-Based Learning" is significant (Beta = 0.60, $p < 0.05$), indicating a positive correlation between play-based learning and empathy development. The beta coefficient's positive value suggests that as play-based learning activities increase, empathy development among nursery school children also improves. Since the p-value is less than 0.05, the null hypothesis H0 3 is rejected, suggesting a significant correlation between play-based learning and empathy development.

Discussion of the Findings

The study revealed a significant correlation between play-based learning and the development of cooperation skills among nursery school children in Southeastern Nigeria, indicated by a positive beta coefficient of 0.58. This finding aligns with previous research that underscores the importance of play in fostering social interactions and collaborative behaviours among young children. Trawick-Smith, Swaminathan, and Liu (2016) emphasize that play-based learning creates a social context where children naturally engage in cooperative activities. Furthermore, Pyle and Danniels (2017) highlight that play-based learning environments encourage children to share responsibilities and work together towards common goals, thereby enhancing their cooperation skills. Similarly, Fisher et al. (2018) found that structured play activities, such as group games and collaborative projects, significantly improve

children's ability to work in teams and share tasks. The rejection of Hypothesis 1 (H0 1) underscores the significant role of play-based learning in fostering cooperation skills, affirming the necessity of integrating play-based strategies in early childhood education to promote social competence and teamwork.

The study also found a significant correlation between play-based learning and the development of sharing skills, with a positive beta coefficient of 0.64. This finding supports existing literature that highlights the role of play in teaching children to share resources and engage in reciprocal interactions. Whitebread et al. (2017) argue that play-based learning provides a context where children practice sharing and turn-taking, which are critical components of prosocial behaviour. Additionally, Elias and Berk (2016) note that play scenarios often require children to negotiate and share materials, fostering a sense of fairness and cooperation. Akinware (2018) further emphasizes that in play-based settings, children learn to empathize with their peers and understand the value of sharing, which enhances their social skills. The rejection of Hypothesis 2 (H0 2) confirms the importance of play-based learning in promoting sharing skills, supporting the implementation of such curricula to enhance social harmony and cooperation among young children.

The positive beta coefficient of 0.60 for the relationship between play-based learning and empathy development indicates a significant positive impact of play-based learning activities on children's ability to understand and share the feelings of others. This finding is consistent with the literature that emphasizes the role of play in promoting emotional understanding and empathy. Whitebread et al. (2017) highlight that play allows children to engage in role-playing and imaginative scenarios, helping them explore different perspectives and develop empathetic responses. Similarly, Denham et al. (2017) assert that through play, children learn to recognize and respond to the emotions of their peers, which is crucial for developing empathy. Obijiofor, Okpala, Nnani, and Nwakile (2020) also found that play-based learning environments support emotional development by providing children with opportunities to practice empathy and understanding in social interactions. The rejection of Hypothesis 3 (H0 3) reinforces the significant correlation between play-based learning and empathy development, highlighting the value of play-based approaches in nurturing emotional and social intelligence in young children.

Conclusion

This study investigated the correlation between play-based learning and social skills development among nursery school children in Southeastern Nigeria, focusing on cooperation, sharing, and empathy. The findings provided significant insights into the effectiveness of play-based learning in early childhood education within this specific cultural context. The study demonstrated a substantial positive correlation between play-based learning and the development of cooperation skills, with a positive beta coefficient indicating that play-based activities significantly enhance children's ability to work collaboratively. Similarly, a significant positive correlation was found between play-based learning and sharing skills, suggesting that play-based approaches effectively promote prosocial behaviours such as sharing and turn-taking. Furthermore, the research unveiled a significant positive correlation between play-based learning and empathy development, highlighting that engaging in play helps children understand and respond to the emotions of others.

These findings underscore the importance of integrating play-based learning strategies in early childhood education to foster essential social skills. The implications are crucial for educators, policymakers, and stakeholders in the educational sector in Southeastern Nigeria. By emphasizing play-based learning, early childhood programs can enhance social competence and holistic development, preparing children for successful interactions in diverse social environments. Investing in play-based curricula and supporting teacher training in these methodologies can create more effective and engaging learning environments for young children. The study's results advocate for policies that prioritize play-based learning, recognizing its significant impact on the social and emotional development of children. Overall, this research contributes valuable knowledge to the global discourse on early childhood education, offering insights that can inform educational practices and policies aimed at nurturing well-rounded and socially competent individuals.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Early childhood education providers should prioritize training programs for educators on the implementation of play-based learning strategies so as to enhance teachers' abilities to

effectively integrate play into the curriculum, thereby fostering the development of cooperation, sharing, and empathy among nursery school children.

2. Policymakers in the education sector should review and adopt policies that support and mandate the incorporation of play-based learning in nursery schools to ensuring that these practices are standard across educational institutions which will promote holistic development and social skills in children.

3. Educational authorities and stakeholders should ensure adequate resources and materials are available for play-based learning activities to encourage interactive and cooperative play.

4. Schools through workshops should engage parents and the community in understanding the benefits of play-based learning which can help parents support and reinforce these practices at home, creating a cohesive learning environment for children.

5. Academic institutions should conduct regular assessments of the effectiveness of play-based learning programs through feedback from teachers, parents, and the children themselves which should be used to continually refine and improve these programs.

Limitations of the Study

While this study provides valuable insights, it is essential to acknowledge certain limitations. These include the potential for response bias in self-reported data by teachers and caregivers, the influence of external factors not accounted for in the research design, and the generalizability of findings beyond Southeastern Nigeria. Future research should aim to address these limitations by incorporating more diverse and representative samples and considering additional contextual factors.

References

- Akinware, M. (2018). Play-based learning in Nigerian preschool education: A review of current practices and prospects. *African Journal of Early Childhood Education*, 6(2), 45-56.
- Barnett, W. S. (2018). Early childhood education and care: An overview of key issues and challenges. *Journal of Early Childhood Research*, 16(2), 157-171.
- Denham, S. A., Bassett, H. H., Brown, C., Way, E., & Steed, J. (2017). "I know how you feel": Preschoolers' emotion knowledge contributes to early school success. *Journal of Early Childhood Research*, 15(2), 190-207.
- Ejeh, M. U. C. (2016). The challenges of early childhood education in Nigeria. *Contemporary Issues in Early Childhood*, 17(2), 233-245.
- Elias, C. L., & Berk, L. E. (2016). Teachers' influence on children's peer interactions: Evidence from research on teacher-child relationships and social-emotional development. *Educational Psychologist*, 51(3-4), 264-276.
- Fisher, K. R., Hirsh-Pasek, K., Newcombe, N. S., & Golinkoff, R. M. (2018). Taking shape: Supporting preschoolers' acquisition of geometric knowledge through guided play. *Child Development*, 84(6), 1872-1878.
- Fleer, M. (2020). Understanding the dialectical relations between everyday concepts and scientific concepts within play-based programs. *Learning, Culture and Social Interaction*, 26, 100 - 109.
- Hughes, C., & Leekam, S. (2017). What do children with autism understand about the mind? A review of theory of mind and social skills development in young children. *Developmental Science*, 10(1), 41-57.

Martlew, J., Stephen, C., & Ellis, J. (2018). Play in the primary school classroom? The experience of teachers supporting children's learning through a new pedagogy. *Early Years*, 28(3), 261-274.

Nwachukwu, C. U., Onah, F.C., Obijiofor, E.O., Nwankwo, C.U. & Nwakile, T.C. (2020). Effects of multiple teaching methods on academic achievement and interest of primary school pupils in agricultural science in Anambra State. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary and Current Research*, 8, (May/ June, 2020 issue), 415 – 420. Available at <http://ijmcr.com/effects-of-multiple-teaching-methods-on-academic-achievement-and-interest-of-primary-school-pupils-in-agricultural-science-in-anambra-state/>

Nwakile, T.C., Umeh, C.R., Shaibu, I.I., Ezeali, M.M. & Ekenta, L.U. (2022). Gender as an intervening variable in comparing effectiveness of teaching methods on the interest of early childhood agricultural science pupils. *International Journal of Recent Research in Social Sciences and Humanities*, 9(3), 145–150. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7100777>

Obijiofor, E.O., Okpala, O. P., Nnani, P.C. & Nwakile, T. C. (2020). The Role of Nutrition in the Developmental Processes of Under-Five Kids in a South-Eastern Nigerian Community: Improving Nutrition of Under-Five Kids through Agriculture. *Asian Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies*, 8(6), 31 – 35. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/342097859>.

Ogunyemi, F. T. (2016). Early childhood education in Nigeria: Issues and challenges. *Journal of Early Childhood Studies*, 10(1), 89-105.

Pyle, A., & Danniels, E. (2017). A continuum of play-based learning: The role of the teacher in play-based pedagogy and the fear of hijacking play. *Early Education and Development*, 28(3), 274-289.

Taguma, M., Litjens, I., & Makowiecki, K. (2016). *Quality matters in early childhood education and care: New Zealand*. OECD Publishing

Trawick-Smith, J., Swaminathan, S., & Liu, X. (2016). The relationship of teacher-child play interactions to mathematics learning in preschool. *Early Childhood Education Journal*, 44(2), 183-191.

Whitebread, D., Basilio, M., Kupalja, M., & Verma, M. (2017). The importance of play in promoting healthy child development and maintaining strong parent-child bonds: Focus on children in poverty. *American Journal of Play*, 9(1), 42-55.